

Project BioCombs4Nanofibers

D3.2 Public report on an example of functional coating on website

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1. Introduction

The overall goal of D3.2 is to provide a public scientific report on an example of functional coating on the materials and structures under investigation in the **BioCombs4Nanofibers** project.

It will be published on the **BioCombs4Nanofibers** website as well as on the Zenodo open data depository. According the deliverable D5.2 Data Management Plan (DMP) - interim, it contains, among others, the fabrication conditions under which different coatings can be obtained and the morphological, chemical, and structural characterization of selected laser- and plasma-fabricated coatings.

In the following sections, functional coatings obtained by laser- and plasma-based techniques are discussed. First, in Section 2, an overview of the samples used for functionalization by laser- and plasma-based techniques are presented. In Section 3 more details on hydrophilic and hydrophobic coatings by matrix-assisted pulsed laser evaporation (MAPLE) are discussed, while in Section 4 an overview of the application of plasma-based methods for the functionalization of surfaces is presented.

2. Laser processed samples for functionalization

Nanosecond (ns) laser-processed poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) specimens with ripples for the application of coatings have been fabricated (Figure 1). These samples are functionalized to become hydrophilic or hydrophobic, and then, the samples will be evaluated for their adhesive properties.

Figure 1: Ripples on ns-laser processed PET samples. The fluence Φ applied was approx. 8.2 mJ/cm^2 . (a) Optical microscopy. (b) SEM image. (c, d) Atomic force micrographs. (e) FFT of micrographs and (f) profile along the white line in (e) in order to assess the periodicity of the ripples.

A PET foil (biaxially stretched; from Goodfellow; $50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thick) has been processed by ns-laser pulses and was characterized by optical microscopy (Figure 1a), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Figure 1b) and atomic force microscopy (AFM) (Figure 1c and d).

The following laser and laser parameters have been used: KrF excimer laser (Lambda Physik); wave length λ : 248 nm ; pulse length τ : 20 ns ; repetition rate: 10 Hz ; 6000 pulses. The samples were irradiated with linearly polarized light under an angle of incidence of $\theta = 30^\circ$. For more information on the setup the reader is referred to (R.-A. Barb *et al.* 2020). The elliptical spot area for ripple generation was approx. 1.4 cm^2 . Two different fluences were applied to the

samples, namely 8.2 mJ/cm² and 5.4 mJ/cm². The absolute energy values were 7.5 - 8 mJ and 10.5 - 11 mJ, respectively. The given pulse energies were measured directly after the lens. At the lower fluence the ns-laser-processed area was found to be more homogeneously covered by ripples, which was confirmed by SEM imaging.

The spatial period of the ripples assessed by fast Fourier transformation (FFT) is 321 nm (Figure 1e and f) and the mean roughness R_a which is a measure for half the ripple height is 27 nm (computed by the free software Gwyddion from AFM images). From single high-resolution AFM images (Figure 1d) the respective spatial period is measured to be 320 nm. The full height of the structures was measured to be approx. 70 nm from exemplary AFM images taken in the non-contact mode.

3. Functional coatings obtained by laser-based techniques

In this section the main findings on laser processing of functional coatings is presented. Hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymer coating was achieved by matrix-assisted pulsed laser evaporation (MAPLE).

1) *The hydrophilic polymer investigated to fabricate coatings is polyethylene oxide (PEO).* PEO is an amphiphilic, water soluble synthetic polyether that is available in a range of molecular weights. PEO is a nontoxic polymer, and it is used in a wide range of applications, in particular in the biomedical field, in drug delivery systems, tissue engineering scaffolds, and surface functionalization.

In the following section we will present a selection of the experiments and characterization steps taken for the optimization of the hydrophilic coatings. We purchased polyethylene oxide (PEO) with an average molecular weight of 100 kDa from Sigma-Aldrich. In order to obtain coatings by MAPLE, PEO solutions were fabricated by dissolving PEO in double distilled water at a concentration of 4 wt%. We first used as substrates double polished silicon substrates Si(100) cut into 1 cm² samples, transparent in the IR for post-characterization. (C.D. Alin *et al.* 2019)

The MAPLE experiments were carried out in a commercial system from Neocera. The 266 nm laser beam from a "Surelite II" pulsed Nd:YAG laser system (Continuum Company) is imaged on the frozen target. When the laser light irradiates this target, the solvent evaporates and the guest material is subsequently collected on the substrate. The substrates are placed at a distance of 3.6 cm from the frozen target.

The substrates were kept at ambient temperature during the deposition. The number of pulses is varied from 12,000 pulses to 126,000, resulting in coatings with variable thicknesses. The target is rotated during the deposition in order to achieve uniform evaporation of the target material.

Once we deposited the PEO coatings, we started characterizing them morphologically, structurally, and compositionally. We acquired XPS survey and high-resolution spectra for the MAPLE deposited PEO coatings by using an Escalab Xi⁺ system, Thermo Scientific. The survey scans are acquired using Al K α gun, with spot size 900 μ m, pass energy of 50.0 eV, energy step size 1.00 eV, and 5 scans, while for the high-resolution XPS spectra the pass energy is set to 20.0 eV, energy step size is 0.10 eV and 10 scans are accumulated.

The survey XPS spectra ranging from 0 to 1200 eV are used to define the elements in the PEO films deposited by MAPLE. The XPS survey spectra shown in Figure 2 indicates that carbon and oxygen are the main elements on the surface of the samples. For a detailed analysis of the surface chemistry of samples, high resolution XPS spectra are recorded in the region of C1s and O1s (Figure 3).

The C1 region is fitted considering five components (C1, C2, C3, C4, C5), which are assigned according to the position of carbon binding energy in PEO. The components are: C=C in sp² (at 284.6 eV); C-H, C-C and in sp³ or defect (at 285.5 eV); C-O and C-C-O single bond (at approximately 286.6 eV); C=O double bonds (at 287.9 eV); and COOH (289.3 eV). In the PEO coatings deposited by MAPLE, we observe the preservation of main carbon bonding in PEO as C-O-C (C3-ether-type carbon) and the CH₂ (polymer backbone-C2) and an additional small percent (~1.5%) of ester and carboxylic acid groups that wasn't present in the other samples. The O1s region was fitted considering the usually binding energy at 531.0 eV (O1, double bond O in O = C), at 533 eV (O2 single bonded O in -O*-C, C-O, HO*-C), and 535.0 eV (O3, attributed to O-COH, COOH).

Contact angle measurements are widely used for the characterization of the hydrophilicity of thin film surfaces. Contact angle measurements are carried out with a KSV CAM101 microscope equipped with a video camera. The contact angle measurements are obtained by applying the sessile drop method, i.e., a syringe is used which disperses double distilled water droplets with a volume of $2.5 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{l}$. Five different points are measured for every thin film and the contact angle reported is the average of these measurements. We found that the as-deposited PEO100 films have a contact angle of $37^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ (see Figure 4a). The surface topography and smoothness of the MAPLE deposited PEO coatings deposited on Si(100) substrates were investigated by non-contact AFM. The as deposited PEO surfaces appear to be rather rough, with a root-mean-square roughness of approx. 150 nm (see Figure 4b).

Relative atomic concentrations of carbon, oxygen		
C1s (%)	O1s (%)	O/C
70.6	29.4	0.42

Figure 2: XPS survey spectra of the PEO coating obtained by MAPLE.

Figure 3: a) XPS of the C1s region for PEO films deposited by MAPLE, and the corresponding fitted deconvolution; b) XPS of the O1s region for the PEO films deposited by MAPLE, and the corresponding fitted deconvolution of the O1s.

Figure 4: a) Photograph of water drops of the PEO coating deposited by MAPLE. b) AFM image on $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$ area of PEO polymer deposited by MAPLE onto Si(100) substrate.

Once the experimental conditions have been optimized, we deposited PEO onto the ns-laser processed PET specimens with ripples. In the images below we show AFM images of the as-processed samples with ripples.

Furthermore, in the table shown below are given the main experimental parameters for coating the ns-laser processed samples with ripples. The PEO coatings were deposited with a Nd:YAG laser system operated at 266 nm wavelength.

Sample	Substrate	Target	Solvent	Φ [mJ/cm ²]	No. laser pulses	Thickness [nm]
1	PET 5 (7.5-8 mJ)	PEO 4%wt	H ₂ O	350	36.000	10
2	PET 4 (10.5-11 mJ)					11

Figure 5: AFM images of the ns-laser processed PET specimens with ripples prior to their coating by MAPLE; a) PET 5 (7.5 - 8 mJ) ripples average height: 113 nm and ripples average width: 333 nm; b) PET 4 (10.5 - 11 mJ) ripples average height: 126 nm and ripples average width: 320 nm.

Figure 6: AFM images of the ns-laser processed PET specimens with ripples coated with PEO polymer by MAPLE; a) ripples average height: 122 nm and ripples average width: 328 nm; b) ripples average height: 70 nm and ripples average width: 314 nm.

FTIR spectrum was recorded with a Nicolet™ FT-IR iS™ 50 spectrometer equipped with an Attenuated Total Reflection (ATR) module as a mean of 16 spectra, at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, and in the spectral range 4000 - 700 cm⁻¹. A ZnSe crystal was used for ATR, having the following characteristics: 1.5 mm diameter, one internal reflection at an incidence angle of 42°, depth of penetration 2.03 μm at 1000 cm⁻¹, and 2.4 refractive index.

The IR spectrum of poly(ethylene oxide) is shown in Figure 7. In the spectrum of the thin film are observed absorption peaks characteristic to PEO at: 3480 cm⁻¹ - O-H stretching vibration of hydroxyl groups, 2885 cm⁻¹ - C-H₂ symmetric stretching of alkane groups, 1466 cm⁻¹ - C-H₂ scissoring vibration in alkane groups, 1343 cm⁻¹ - C-H₂ wagging vibration in alkane groups, 1280 and 1241 - C-H₂ twisting vibration in alkane groups, 1112 cm⁻¹ - C-O-C asymmetric stretching vibration in ethers, 964 cm⁻¹ - combination between C-H₂ scissoring and rocking vibration in alkane groups, 876 cm⁻¹, 843 cm⁻¹, and 816 cm⁻¹ - C-O symmetric stretching vibration in ethers groups, and 739 cm⁻¹ - C-C skeleton vibration (rocking). This absorption bands are in accordance with that of the starting sample, before laser deposition. obtained by drop cast.

Figure 7: FTIR-ATR spectra of poly(ethylene oxide) in the form of thin film, drop, and powder in the: a) spectral range 4000 - 700 cm^{-1} ; b) spectral range 1800 - 700 cm^{-1} .

Furthermore, a new absorption band with peak at 1719 cm^{-1} was observed, corresponding to carbonyl ester group and suggesting the oxidation of terminal group $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ to the $-\text{COOH}$ group. This peak was not identified in the IR spectra of poly(ethylene oxide) in powder formed or dissolved in water and applied via drop cast method suggesting that the oxidation occurred during MAPLE deposition of poly(ethylene oxide).

A collaboration with colleagues from **ELI-NP** was established to qualify the MAPLE technique for its capabilities to laser-functionalize surfaces with hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymer coatings.

Our colleagues from ELI are using the HELIOS software to model the interaction of a laser beam with frozen targets in MAPLE. In particular, they are first looking at the interaction of laser beams with different wavelengths with solid frozen H_2O targets (the most common in MAPLE, and the one used to deposit the PEO polymer) in order to assess the influence of the laser wavelength on the solvent chosen for the MAPLE experiments.

The results obtained in collaboration with colleagues from **ELI-NP** will contribute to a scientific publication, acknowledging the support of this EU project. The preliminary project-related results are shown below in Figures 8 – 10.

Figure 8: The plasma pressure inside the frozen H₂O target. This corresponds to a plasma fluid velocity of 10^7 cm/s at the front side of the target.

Figure 9: The plasma expansion at the front side target. The shock wave induced by the laser pulse is observed travelling inside the target.

Figure 10: Plot of the corresponding electron temperatures of the expanded plasma and inside the frozen target.

b) The hydrophobic polymer investigated to fabricate coatings is polyvinyl formal (PVF).

In this section we will present a selection of the experiments and characterization steps taken for the deposition of the hydrophobic coatings. We purchased polyvinyl formal (PVF) from Sigma-Aldrich (also named Vinylec K). In order to obtain coatings by MAPLE, PVF solutions were fabricated by dissolving PVF in acetic acid at a concentration of 2 wt%. We first used as substrates double polished silicon substrates Si(100) cut into 1 cm² samples, transparent in the IR for post-characterization.

The MAPLE experiments were carried out in a commercial system from Neocera. The 266 nm laser beam from a “Surelite II” pulsed Nd:YAG laser system (Continuum Company) is imaged on the frozen target. When the laser light irradiates this target, the solvent evaporates and the guest material is subsequently collected on the substrate. The substrates are placed at a distance of 3.6 cm from the frozen target.

The substrates were kept at ambient temperature during the deposition. The number of pulses is varied from 12,000 pulses to 126,000, resulting in coatings with variable thicknesses. The target is rotated during the deposition in order to achieve uniform evaporation of the target material.

The experimental conditions used to deposit the PVF coating onto the ns-laser processed samples with ripples are shown in the table below.

Sample	Substrate	Target	Solvent	ϕ [mJ/cm ²]	No. laser pulses	Thickness [nm]
3 JKU	PET 6 (7.5-8 mJ)	PVF (2%)	Acetic acid	450	36.000	97
4 JKU	PET 3 (10.5-11 mJ)				36.000	92

First, atomic force microscopy (AFM) (XE 100 AFM setup from Park) measurements are carried out to analyse the films thickness as well as surface roughness on several different areas and dimensions. The images obtained from the AFM are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: AFM images of the ns-laser processed PET specimens with ripples coated with PVF polymer by MAPLE; a) ripples average height: 125 nm and ripples average width: 315 nm; b) ripples average height: 123 nm and ripples average width: 314 nm.

The PEO coating is very thin (around 10 nm) therefore the ripples on PET keep the shapes and sizes. Even if the PVF coatings on PET are thicker (around 100 nm) the ripples have the same sizes and shapes as the ripples form PET substrate. The polymer coatings are continuous, covering the hole deposited area. Small and rare droplets of polymers can be observed on the surfaces.

The IR spectrum of poly(vinyl formal) is shown in Figure 12. In the spectrum of the thin film are observed absorption peaks characteristic to PVF at: 3456 cm^{-1} - O-H stretching vibration, 2980 cm^{-1} - C-H asymmetric stretching vibration in CH_2 groups, 2940 cm^{-1} - C-H asymmetric stretching vibration in CH_3 groups, 2916 cm^{-1} - C-H asymmetric stretching vibration in CH_2 groups, 2860 cm^{-1} - C-H symmetric stretching vibration in CH_2 groups, 1718 cm^{-1} - C=O vibration of acetate unit $-\text{O}-\text{C}=\text{O}$, 1437 cm^{-1} and 1405 cm^{-1} - C-H asymmetric stretching vibration in CH_3 groups, 1389 cm^{-1} and 1367 cm^{-1} - C-H symmetric stretching vibration in CH_3 groups, 1235 cm^{-1} - C-H wagging vibration, 1169 cm^{-1} and 1106 cm^{-1} - C-O-C stretching vibration, $-1023-820\text{ cm}^{-1}$ C-O symmetric stretching vibration, and 783 cm^{-1} C-O stretching and rocking vibration.

The absorption bands of the IR spectrum of PVF matched those identified in the IR spectra of powder form or dissolved in acetic acid and applied *via* drop cast method, confirming the deposition of PVF using the MAPLE method.

Figure 12: FTIR-ATR spectra of poly(vinyl formal) in the form of thin film, drop, and powder in the: a) spectral range 4000-700 cm^{-1} ; b) spectral range 1800-700 cm^{-1} .

4. Functional coatings obtained by plasma-based techniques

In order to obtain functionalized surfaces, i.e., with a tunable surface chemistry, an advanced plasma method for functionalization can be applied. This method is based on cold atmospheric pressure radiofrequency plasma source and is applicable to both polymeric and metallic samples. The developed plasma source produces a linear plasma, and is compatible with scanning of planar samples. An image of the plasma generated by the source is shown in Figure 13. The produced plasma has about 10 cm length and 2 mm width.

The experiments were carried out with the following parameters: Argon gas flow rate 3000 sccm, RF power 30 W. The processing experiments were carried out in ambient atmosphere. The samples were fixed on a horizontal holder and submitted to a variable number of scans (various equivalent exposure times), with plasma positioned at 2 mm above the surface. The scanning speed was 6 mm/sec, which corresponds to an exposure time of the surface of about 170 ms per scan.

Figure 13: Treatment geometry: both the untreated and laser treated zones were scanned by plasma.

The surface modification was evaluated by contact angle measurements, sessile drop method, each result representing an average of independent measurements in 3 different points. Thus, the average values and errors of the contact angle on the polymeric foil in the laser unexposed and laser exposed areas were:

Sample	Sample code	Comments
PET 1 (10.5 – 11 mJ)	P1_10.5_m	Unexposed zone substrate (foil)
	P1_10.5_L	Laser exposed zone
	P1_10.5_m_PL1	Plasma (1 scan, 170 ms) exposed zone
	P1_10.5_L_PL1	Laser and plasma (1 scan) exposed zone
	P1_10.5_m_PL5	Plasma (5 scans, 850 ms) exposed zone
	P1_10.5_L_PL5	Laser and plasma (5 scans, 850 ms) exposed zone
PET 3 (7.5 – 8 mJ)	P3_7.5_m	Unexposed zone substrate (foil)
	P3_7.5_L	Laser exposed zone
	P3_7.5_m_PL1	Plasma (1 scan, 170 ms) exposed zone
	P3_7.5_L_PL1	Laser and plasma (1 scan) exposed zone
	P3_7.5_m_PL5	Plasma (5 scans, 850 ms) exposed zone
	P3_7.5_L_PL5	Laser and plasma (5 scans, 850 ms) exposed zone

Figure 14: Contact angle values for the untreated polymeric foils, plasma processed, laser processed, and laser plus plasma cases.

Contact angle values for different zones and treatment conditions

Sample Code	Water contact angles (°)					
	Unexposed zone substrate (foil)	Laser exposed zone	Plasma (1 scan) exposed zone	Laser and plasma (1 scan) exposed zone	Plasma (5 scans) exposed zone	Laser and plasma (5 scans) exposed zone
PET 1 – (10.5 – 11 mJ)	89.16 ± 5.24	74.12 ± 3.94	82.53 ± 12.49	58.09 ± 8.75	57.91 ± 3.92	17.58 ± 4.78
CONCLUSIONS Additional comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The contact angle values decrease from 89.16 ° to 74.12 ° after laser exposure For the unexposed zone substrate (foil), the contact angle values decreased from 89.16 ° to 82.53 ° after one scan and to 57.91 ° after 5 scans, indicating an increase of the surface wettability after plasma treatments A similar trend was observed for the laser exposed zone, as the contact angle values decreased from 74.12 ° to 58.09 ° and 17.58 ° after plasma treatments of 1 and 5 scans, respectively The differences between the initial and the final contact angle values (after plasma treatment – 5 scans) are ~31 ° for the unexposed substrate and ~56 ° for the laser exposed zone, indicating a better efficiency of the plasma treatment for the laser exposed zone regarding the increase of the surface wettability 					
PET 3 (7.5 – 8 mJ)	79.44 ± 8.85	39.72 ± 10.44	72.02 ± 3.95	31.57 ± 4.48	47.27 ± 7.23	12.14 ± 0.87

<p>CONCLUSIONS</p> <p>Additional comments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The contact angle values decrease from 79.44° to 39.72° after laser exposure • For the unexposed zone substrate (foil), the contact angle values decreased from 79.44° to 72.02° after one scan and to 47.27° after 5 scans, indicating an increase of the surface wettability after plasma treatments • A similar trend was observed for the laser exposed zone, as the contact angle values decreased from 39.72° to 31.57° and 12.14° after plasma treatments of 1 and 5 scans, respectively • The differences between the initial and the final contact angle values (after plasma treatment – 5 scans) are ~32° for the unexposed substrate and ~27° for the laser exposed zone, indicating a better efficiency of the plasma treatment for the unexposed zone regarding the increase of the surface wettability; however, the difference of ~5° is not as relevant as the difference of ~25° observed for the sample 1 (10.5 -11 mJ)
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5. References

(C.D. Alin *et al.* 2019) Alin, C.D.; Grama, F.; Papagheorghe, R.; Brajnicov, S; Ion, V.; Vizireanu, S.; Palla-Papavlu, A.; Dinescu, M., Tuning the physicochemical properties of hernia repair meshes by matrix-assisted pulsed laser evaporation, *Applied Physics A* (2019) 125:424

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6. Conclusions

All goals described in the introduction are still valid and will be pursued further in the course of the project. As the overall aim is to study the interaction of the bio-inspired surfaces with natural and artificial nanofibers, the next step will be to measure the adhesive properties of the coatings functionalized by laser and plasma techniques.

This report has been published as a public report (PDF) entitled “Public report on an example of functional coating on website” in the dissemination section of the website of the **BioCombs4Nanofibers** project (<http://biocombs4nanofibers.eu>) as well as on the Zenodo open data depository.

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